

Surface rotation of *Kepler* solar-type stars

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Abstract

Dark spots crossing the stellar disk lead to periodic modulations in stellar light-curves that encode information on surface rotation and magnetic activity. Here, we analyze *Kepler* long-cadence data (four different time-series) for $\sim 50,000$ solar-type main-sequence and subgiant stars cooler than 5500 K and with surface gravity $\log g$ larger than 3.5 dex. Surface rotation period estimates are obtained through the implementation of a method which combines a wavelet analysis with the autocorrelation of the light-curve. We obtain reliable rotation periods for 23,494 stars. Only $\sim 16,600$ of these are common to McQuillan *et al.* (2013a, 2014), with an agreement of $\sim 99\%$ within 2σ . We also take special care to identify and remove possible polluters, such as classical pulsators, misclassified Red Giants, photometric pollution and other instrumental issues in light-curves.

1 Introduction

Stellar rotation is an important ingredient for the generation of magnetic fields and magnetic cycles in the Sun and solar-type stars (e.g. Brun & Browning, 2017). Moreover, as stars evolve they are observed to slowdown (e.g. Wilson, 1963; Wilson & Skumanich, 1964). Therefore, surface rotation can be used as proxy for stellar age (gyrochronology; Skumanich, 1972; Barnes, 2007).

Stellar surface rotation can be retrieved from brightness variations due to the presence of dark spots crossing the visible stellar disk (e.g. Reinhold *et al.*, 2013; Nielsen *et al.*, 2013; McQuillan *et al.*, 2013a,b, 2014; García *et al.*, 2014a; Ceillier *et al.*, 2016, 2017).

In this work, we study brightness variations of more than 50,000 *Kepler* (Borucki *et al.*, 2010) main-sequence and subgiant stars in order to determine their surface rotation. This analysis will be presented in detail in Santos *et al.* (in prep).

2 Sample selection and data preparation

In this work, we analyze *Kepler* long cadence data of main-sequence and subgiant stars with effective temperature, T_{eff} , lower than 5500 K and surface gravity, $\log g$, larger than 3.5 dex according to *Kepler* Stellar Properties Catalog for Data Release 25 (KSPC DR25; Mathur *et al.*, 2017). Figure 1 shows the Kiel-Diagram for the target sample which comprises 50,032 stars.

In this work, we use three sets of KADACS (*Kepler* Asteroseismic Data Analysis and Calibration Software; García *et al.*, 2011) light-curves obtained from *Kepler* long-cadence ($\Delta t = 29.42$ min) data. KADACS corrects for instrumental artifacts and properly concatenates the different *Kepler* Quarters. The light-curves are also interpolated using in-painting

Figure 1: Kiel-diagram for the target sample, color coded by number of stars in a given parameter range.

techniques (García *et al.*, 2014b; Pires *et al.*, 2015) and high-pass filtered at 20, 55 and 80 days¹.

For comparison, we also analyze the PDC-MAP (Presearch Data Conditioning - Maximum A Posteriori; e.g. Jenkins *et al.*, 2010) time-series.

3 Surface rotation estimate

Surface rotation estimates are obtained by implementing the methodology described by Ceillier *et al.* (2016, 2017) which combines wavelet analysis (e.g. Torrence & Compo, 1998; Mathur *et al.*, 2010) and the autocorrelation function (e.g. McQuillan *et al.*, 2013a; García *et al.*, 2014a) of the light-curve. This method was tested in a hare-and-hounds exercise

¹KADACS light-curves will be soon publicly available at MAST - Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes.

in Aigrain *et al.* (2015) and was found to be the best method in terms of completeness and reliability.

Two rotation period estimates are obtained directly from the global wavelet power spectrum (GWPS; e.g. Mathur *et al.*, 2010, 2014) and autocorrelation function (ACF; e.g. García *et al.*, 2014a). An additional estimate is recovered from the composite spectrum (CS; Ceillier *et al.*, 2016, 2017) which is the product between the GWPS and the ACF and is sensitive to the periods present in both diagnostics.

A first group of targets with reliable rotation estimates is selected automatically if the results agree between the three diagnostics and the three KADACS data sets, and if the amplitude of the rotation peaks in the ACF and CS is larger than a given threshold (adopted from Ceillier *et al.*, 2017).

The remaining targets are then visually inspected and additional rotation estimates retrieved. We also visually check the targets for which the results from KADACS and PDC-MAP time-series do not agree.

We remove from the analysis known eclipsing binaries and RR Lyrae stars. We identify and remove misclassified Red Giants, including those identified by Berger *et al.* (2018). We identify light-curves showing photometric pollution which can indicate the presence of nearby stars or binary systems. Finally, we also flag targets that do not behave as typical active stars. Those are fast rotators ($P_{\text{rot}} < 7$ days) and are possible classical pulsator candidates or possible close-in binary systems (see for example Simonian *et al.*, 2018).

4 Results and discussion

We successfully recover surface rotation periods P_{rot} for 23,494 targets ($\sim 47\%$ of the sample). An additional 5,037 targets ($\sim 10\%$ of the sample) show evidence for spot modulation, but no reliable rotation periods were obtained for those stars. No evidence for spot modulation is detected for 14,078 targets (28% of the sample).

We find that targets without spot modulation are on average fainter than targets with spot modulation, while the targets that we identify as possible classical pulsators are on average brighter.

The results are consistent with M stars being slower rotators than K stars, which in turn are slower rotators than G stars. This is also shown in Figure 2, which is in good agreement with the results shown in McQuillan *et al.* (2014, the agreement between P_{rot} estimates is 99% for the 16,649 common stars). We find that rotation period decreases with increasing effective temperature. Also, our results confirm the bi-modality found by McQuillan *et al.* (2014) seen through the two tails for the coolest targets and by the two high density regions for the hottest targets. We note that our target sample has 32,455 stars ($\sim 60\%$ of the sample) that are not included in the analysis by McQuillan *et al.* (2013a, 2014).

A more detailed description of the analysis and results for K and M main-sequence stars will be provided in Santos *et al.* (in prep).

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Figure 2: Rotation period as a function of effective temperature color coded by number of stars in a given bin.

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